

A Review of Polymer and Their Blends: Classifications & Applications

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Abstract:

Polymer and their blends are a very important class of materials. As these materials plays vital role in day today life so it is necessary to study. Polymer material classified according to the mechanical response and basis of electrolytes system. Variation in polymeric properties mainly depends upon there synthesis methods and deposition techniques. So, various synthesis methods and deposition techniques are mention. USP (unique selling point) of polymeric materials are there application in various sector such as Electronic devices and batteries applications, in membranes such a range of industrial applications and also polymers are essential components of many drug delivery systems and biomedical products.

Keywords: Polymer, Polymer blends, Electrolytes, Applications

1. Introduction

Polymer material plays vital role in day today life. Polymer materials and their blends has varies applications in many areas e,g electrochemical devices batteries, fuel cells, super capacitor, sensors and insulating materials [1-4]. So, it is important to study ice-break material like solid polymer and polymer electrolytes. To study the basic of the polymers and their polyblends is essential.

2. Polymer

Polymers form a very important class of materials without which the life seems very difficult. They are all around us in our everyday use e.g. in rubber, in plastic, in resins, and in adhesives and adhesives tapes. The word polymer is derived from Greek words, poly = many and mers = parts or units of high molecular mass each molecule of which consist of a very large number of single structural units joined together in a regular manner. In other words polymers are giant molecules of high molecular weight, called macromolecules, which are build up by linking together of a large number of small molecules, called monomers. The reaction by which the monomers combine to form polymer is known as polymerization [5]. The polymerization is chemical reaction in which two or more substances combine together with or without evolution of anything like water, heat or any other solvents to form a molecule of high molecular weight. The product is called polymer and the starting material is called monomer.

Every polymer has its own characteristics, but most polymers have the following general properties. They have low density, low coefficient of friction, good corrosion resistance, good mouldability, economical, poor tensile strength, low mechanical properties, and poor temperature resistance. It can be resistant to chemicals and also to both thermal and electrical insulators. Generally, polymers are light in weight with varying degrees of strength. Polymers can be processed in various ways to produce thin fibers or intricate parts.

Polymer electrolytes are plastic materials that can be modified and processed by conventional techniques. If the polymer chains are helped for a charge transport of the ionic type, often called "polymer electrolyte". In general, polymer electrolytes are used as separator and they are used for ionic transport. In recent years, Polymer electrolytes have attracted

scientific and technological importance because of their potential applications. The idea of preparation of polymer electrolytes was first proposed by Wright [6, 7] and Fenton *etal* in 1973 [8, 9] but their technological significances are fulfilled and appreciated by Armand *etal* [10] few years later. Poly (ethylene oxide) was the first solvating polymer to be proposed and studied in solid polymer electrolyte (SPE) Li-rechargeable batteries [11, 12]. Most of the solid polymer electrolytes (SPEs) are prepared by dissolving lithium salts in a solvating polymer in a common solvent or by diffusion in the solid (or) molten state. An effort is also made to fix or immobilize the anion on the polymer matrix by covalent bonding (or) another chemical or physical process [13]. In the present work, an attempt has been made to develop the polymer electrolytes based on PVAc.

2.1 Classification of Polymer on Basis of Mechanical Properties

Polymers may be classified as follows, according to the mechanical response at elevated temperatures [6].

Flow-chart 1. Classifications of Polymer

2.2 Classification of Polymer on Basis of Electrolytes System

The polymer electrolyte systems [14] could be classified into three categories, namely, Polyelectrolyte, Solvent swollen polymer electrolyte and Solvent free polymer electrolytes. Solvent free polymer electrolytes means that polymer –salt complexes which are formed by complexes between salts of alkali metals and polymer containing solvating heteroatoms such as O, N, S, etc. The most common examples are complexation between poly (ethylene oxide) (PEO) and alkali metal salts. The polymer salt complexes are further classified into: a) Solid polymer electrolytes b) Blend polymer electrolytes c) Gel polymer electrolytes d) Composite polymer electrolytes.

2.3 Synthesis and Deposition Methods for Polymers and Polyblends

Methods for synthesis and deposition of polymer thin films and their polyblends are: Langmuir Blodgett (LB) Technique [15], Gas phase deposition technique [16], Solvent evaporation [17], Vacuum evaporation technique [18], Isothermal evaporation technique [19-20], Spin Coating [21-22], Plasma Polymerization [23], Laser lithography [24] and etc.

3. Applications of Polymers and Their Blends

3.1 Electronic Devices and Batteries

Polymers are already playing a critical role in saving energy and resources across a variety of applications, such as transport, packaging, healthcare, and buildings [25]. Polymer scientists are conducting a great deal of research into the potential for polymers to provide cutting-edge renewable energy technologies. Such avenues are photovoltaic, fuel cell, polymer semiconductors, LED (light-emitting diode), etc. Polymer and polymer blends elucidates some important polymers thoughtful effort of elaborating various such energy application schemes in line with the energy assembly, energy storage, dye sensitized electric cell, light emitting and sensing, perovskite electric cell, thermoelectrical generator, polymer composite for

thermoelectrical generator, piezoelectric, triboelectric generator, and supercapacitor have been discussed for better understanding of the readers [26].

3.2 Polymer Blends in Membranes

It is intended to highlight here possible ways of improvement the properties of polymeric membranes, by modifying with other polymers, functional groups, compounds, drugs, bioactive components, and nanomaterials. Polymeric membranes are widely used in a range of industrial applications, such as desalination, wastewater treatment, bio-purification/separation, solvent purification/recovery, gas and liquid phase pollutant capture, and gas separations [27].

3.3 Polymer Blends in Drug Delivery

Polymers are essential components of many drug delivery systems and biomedical products [28].

4. Conclusion

Polymer and polymer blended material are an effectively synthesis and deposited. These fabricated new versatile materials have potential applications in various sectors such as drug delivery, electronic devices and batteries and etc.

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